

A PROJECT REPORT ON MODELING AND ROBUST CONTROL OF BLU-RAY DISC SERVO MECHANISMS

BY

MANU MITRA

0795410

UNIVERSITY OF BRIDGEPORT

2008-2009

Name : - *Manu Mitra*

Student Id : - *0795410*

Major : - *Electrical Engineering*

Class : - *Mechatronics*

Subject : - *Project Report on Modeling and robust control of Blu-Ray disc servo-mechanisms*

Submission : - *July 10th 2009*

Comments:-

Marks Obtained

Professor's Signature.

Contents

1. Modeling and robust control of Blu-ray disc servo-mechanisms

1.0 Abstract

1.1 Introduction

1.2 Performance requirements in BD's

1.2.1 Track Disturbances

1.2.2 Specifications: maximum tracking errors

1.2.3 The reference servo

1.3 Modeling of the coupling effect

1.3.1 Radial sensitivity function and disturbances

1.3.2 Focus sensitivity function and disturbances

1.4 Experimental validation

1.4.1 Set-up description

1.4.2 Computation of the sensitivities

1.5 Reducing the coupling effect by h^∞ control

1.5.1 Mixed-sensitivity h^∞ controller design

1.5.2 Simulation results using experimental data

1.5.3 Uncertainty modeling and robustness analysis

1.5.4 Uncertain modeling

1.5.5 Robust stability and performance analysis

1.6 Conclusion

2. How does Laser works

2.0 Introduction

2.1 The Basics of an Atom

2.2 Absorbing Energy

2.3 The Laser/Atom Connection

2.4 Properties of Laser Light

2.5 Ruby Lasers

2.6 Laser Classifications

2.6.1 Gas lasers

2.6.2 Chemical lasers

2.6.3 Dye lasers

2.6.4 Metal-vapor lasers

2.6.5 Solid-state lasers

2.6.6 Semiconductor lasers

2.6.7 Other types of lasers

3. How does CD WORK?

3.0 Introduction

3.1 Understanding the CD: Material

3.1.1 Understanding the CD: The Spiral

3.1.2 Understanding the CD: Bumps

3.2 CD player Components

4. How does DVDs work?

4.0 Introduction

4.1 DVD Disks

4.2 DVD Layers

4.3 DVD Storage Capacities

4.3.1 Higher Density Data Storage

4.3.2 Less Overhead, More Area

4.3.3 Multi-Layer Storage

4.4 DVD Video

4.4.1 The MPEG-2 Format and Data Size Reduction

4.5 DVD Audio

5. Blue Laser

5.0 Introduction

5.1 History

5.2 Applications

6. How does Blu ray Disc Works?

6.0 Introduction

6.1 Building a Blu-ray Disc

6.2 How Blu-ray reads Data?

6.2.1 Formats

6.3 Blu-ray Competitors

Modeling and robust control of Blu-ray disc servo-mechanisms

1.0 Abstract:

This project deals with the modeling and the robust control of the next generation of optical disc drives servo-mechanisms. While in many industrial servo-control implementations, the radial and focus loops are considered as decoupled, e.g. DVD drives, this is no longer true for HD-DVD and Blu-ray disc (BD) formats which are more sensitive to opto-mechanical interactions at high frequencies. The impact of such phenomena on the robustness of the servo is evaluated by using experimental data, and an h_{∞} controller is designed to reduce the coupling effect, by using a suitable disturbance model into the problem formulation. Simulations using experimental data illustrate the performance improvement of the compensated system despite the parametric uncertainties in mass-production optical drives.

1.1 Introduction:

The advances of new display technologies such as liquid crystal, plasma and liquid crystal on silicon in consumer electronic terminals, large high-definition (HD) screens will become increasingly affordable. A natural next step will be wider adoption of HD imaging. However, this will also depend upon the availability of suitable removable storage media to contain the large volumes of data required for distribution of feature-length films and other HD content. The blu-ray Disc (BD) is a next generation optical disk data format developed by a group of leading consumer electronics and personal computer companies including BLAZE partners Philips and Thomson now known as the Blu-ray Disc Association. Because the technology uses blue lasers, which have shorter wave length than traditional red lasers, BD makes it possible to store substantially more data than existing CDs or DVDs on the same amount of physical space. Consequently it is likely to become a universal standard for video distribution, hybrid networking and streaming media applications, making it an essential component of future home entertainment systems and portable appliances.

A major innovation is that Blu-ray is aiming to store 50 GB on a dual-layer disc of CD format through innovate high numerical aperture optics and new low cost, high resolution recording material. Further innovations in optics, drive technology and cost-effective trans-coding chips will be required as multiple HD video standards emerge globally. High numerical aperture optics and new low cost, high resolution recording material. Further innovations in optics, drive technology and cost-effective trans-coding chips will be required as multiple HD video standards emerge globally. High numerical aperture lenses and shorter wavelength lasers will narrow the servo margins substantially. Methods of getting around this, will give rise to a variety of servo and reliability issues to be solved. The main control problem in the CD-based mechanisms concerns the control of the radial and axial (for focus) position of the laser beam, the role of which is to read optical coded information from the disc. This task becomes more difficult for non perfect discs, as the optical disc deformations cause undesired perturbations in the vertical and radial control servos. The accurate positioning of the laser spot in both directions should be achieved despite of the presence of such disturbances (for which only the maximal magnitude is known). Advanced robust control is therefore unavoidable to ensure the track following with suitable accuracy.

Although in current industrial control implementations the radial and focus loops are considered as decoupled, in practice there are several causes of interaction, e.g. mechanical, electro-magnetic and/or optical cross-coupling. The radial control-loop cannot see the grooves until the focus control-loop is locked and disc in focus. The grooves show up in the focus signal. Decoupling of the focus and radial signals depends upon proper alignment of detectors. Any slight misalignment leads to cross coupling.

Contrary to the CD and DVD formats, this problem becomes relevant in HD-DVD and BD formats, because the system should guarantee much more performance in presence of similar disc deformations by using limited bandwidth controllers. Thus, the problem suggests exploring new alternatives to improve performances, using more accurate models of perturbations and designing less conservative controllers.

Some works have been performed in modeling and identification of opto-mechanical interactions in DVDs. In a study of the control loop coupling is made.

It is found that at low frequencies the dynamic interaction between the focus and the radial loop is negligible with respect to the main disturbances (eccentricity is negligible with respect to the main disturbances (eccentricity and tilt), as it is also stated in. In fact, instead of the radial arm in first versions of CD mechanisms, today all DVD drives use a linear actuator to minimize the optical cross couplings. However, this phenomenon is still important at high frequencies. It is shown how the optical sensors affect the measured error signals, producing cross-coupling between focus and radial loops. An interesting model of an optical disc drive is presented in; where authors show that the mechanical coupling is mainly caused by manufacturing tolerances and alignment errors. This aspect suggests that the coupling is more significant for a demand disc. The impact of such mechanical coupling over the drive performance is not well explained, and studies are scarce. Thus, engineers in the optical Disc Drive industry often encounter these associated problems, which are so significant that the controller tuning becomes a laborious work in order to avoid the performance degradation.

This project is concerned with robust control for HD-DVD and BD formats which have not been tackled yet. It follows our preliminary results on disturbance modeling in optical disc drives. This disturbance model takes into account the opto-mechanical coupling between radial and vertical control loops. Here the experimental validation of this model is provided through the analysis of the closed loop tracking errors. Then, a new robust h controller is designed using the previous disturbance model with the objective to reduce the coupling effect. Finally a robust stability and performance analysis is provided with respect to parameters uncertainties which emphasize the interest if h control in this frame-work.

1.2 Performance requirements in BD's

In a CD-based mechanism, the laser beam position (axial and radial) is controlled by two servo mechanisms, often called as the Focus and Radial servos. Fig.1 depicts the control scheme, where both radial and focus control loops are included, i.e. every signal into the scheme should be interpreted as two-dimensional vectors. The control input $u \triangleq [u_R \ u_F]$; the laser beam position $r \triangleq [x \ z]$; the track disturbance (i.e. track position) $r_{ref} \triangleq [X_{ref} \ Z_{ref}]$; and tracking error $r \triangleq [x \ z]$.

On the other hand, the block $K(s)$ represents the controllers (i.e. K_f : focus controller, and K_R : radial controller), given as follows in current industrial solutions:

$$K(s) = \begin{pmatrix} KR(s) & 0 \\ 0 & KF(s) \end{pmatrix}. \quad \dots (1)$$

The actuators (or plants to be controlled) are described as follows:

Fig. 1. The optical disc drive control loop.

$$G(s) = \begin{pmatrix} GR(s) & 0 \\ 0 & GF(s) \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where G_R and G_F correspond to the actuators transfer functions for radial and focus, respectively.

Notice that the controllers could be in general independently designed for uncoupled radial and focus actuators, and then, we might think that there is not coupling between these controllers and/or actuators. In fact, in the proposed framework, the coupling will appear as output disturbances affecting the independent control loops.

1.2.1 Track Disturbances

In optical disc drives the servos are designed in such a way that the recorded information into the optical disc could be recovered correctly in an optimal way (reasonable time and precision). Nevertheless, to recover digital data in the optical disc the servos are forced to reject strong disturbances using only information about the current tracking error \bar{r} obtained through a Focus and a Radial error

generators. The Fig.2 illustrates a track disturbance spectrum obtained experimentally in.

Due to the rotary nature of the CD-based mechanisms, the most important sources of disturbances concern those that present a periodic behavior. The main sources could be summarized as:

- The vertical deviations (i.e. the vertical movement of the optical pickup unit when the disc rotates) are generally produced by disc tilt and/or warping.
- The radial deviations are mainly produced by the disc eccentricity which corresponds to the distance variation between the geometrical center of the data track and the center hole of the disc.

Fig. 2. Disturbance spectrum obtained at fixed disc rotation frequency of 33 Hz. Dash lines are the allowed disturbance for a DVD drive.

- The disc eccentricity could be also another source of vertical deviation due to the mechanical coupling of the laser beam. In general this vertical deviation contribution is very small and often negligible.

Fig. 3 illustrates the geometry of a disc affected by both radial disc tilt and disc eccentricity. Table 1 summarizes the main vertical and radial disturbance source and magnitudes (present at low frequencies).

1.2.2 Specifications: maximum tracking errors

In presence of disturbances the Radial and Focus servos are required guarantee certain performance level during playback. That is, the focus of the optical beam shall have a maximum axial deviation:

$$\bar{z}_{\max} \triangleq \max |z(t)| = \frac{l}{2.NA^2}, \quad \dots (3)$$

From the recording layer, and it shall have a maximal radial deviation:

$$\bar{x}_{\max} \triangleq \max |\bar{x}(t)| = 0.1q, \quad \dots (4)$$

from the center of a groove or a land recording track. $\bar{z}(t)$ and $\bar{x}(t)$ stand for the instantaneous tracking errors. Constants l , NA and q represent some drive parameters. Table 2 provides some DVD and BD parameters values and their corresponding symbol definitions in Eqs. (3) and (4).

The maximum magnitude of the tracking errors, in both DVD and BD drives, are summarized in Table 3.

Remark that the size of the allowed tracking errors in the BD radial servo is $\frac{1}{2}$ that of the DVD, while the size of the allowed tracking errors in the BD focus servo is $\frac{1}{3}$ that allowed in DVD's. This aspect suggests paying attention to the improvement of the focus servo performance i.e. the disturbance attenuation at higher frequencies (proportional to the reference linear velocity).

Fig. 3. Disc geometry affected by disc tilt and disc eccentricity.

Table 1

Disturbance magnitudes in BD and DVD servos at low frequencies.

Type of disturbance	Symbol	Max. value
Max. vertical deviation:	z_{dmax}	500 μm
Max. radial runout:	x_{dmax}	70 μm

Table 2

Optical disc drive parameters [20].

Parameters	Symbol	DVD	BD
Wavelength	λ :	650 nm	405 nm
Numerical aperture	NA:	0.6	0.85
Track pitch	q :	0.74 μm	0.32 μm
Reference linear velocity	v_a :	3.49 m/s	5.28 m/s
Min. radial position	x_{min} :	24 mm	24 mm
Max. radial position	x_{max} :	58 mm	58 mm

Table 3

Maximal tracking errors.

Max. allowed tracking errors	Symbol	DVD	BD
Max. axial (Focus) error:	z_{max}	0.903 μm	0.280 μm
Max. radial error:	x_{max}	0.074 μm	0.032 μm

Fig. 4. Required disturbance attenuation for the Focus servo [7].

1.2.3 The reference servo

The design of a given disc drive controller is done through a translation of time-domain ones, based on a theoretical disturbance model. These specifications are represented with the dashed lines in Fig.2. The Reference Servo is a well defined transfer function which describes how attenuation would be met (see for example the Standard ECMA-267). But any optical or mechanical coupling is taken into account the absolute estimated value of disturbances without regarding their origin. This ideal shape of the sensitivity function is shown in Fig.4. Thus, the control problem is to design a controller $K(s)$ such that the performance specifications described in the Table 3 are met during presence of strong disturbances described in the Table 1. That is, the sensitivity functions of the controlled system (Radial and Focus servos) should stay below a given reference curve, e.g. Fig.4. Therefore, to achieve an improved control design we will require a more accurate disturbance model.

1.3 Modeling of the coupling effect

In DVD and BD drives the optical error measurements are observed by using the astigmatic method for focus tracking error and the push-pull method for radial tracking error. Actually the measurements are obtained from a single quad-photodiode detector, which in fact, is the only available sensor for keeping the spot in track.

There are several sources of coupling effects; they can be due to mechanical, electro-magnetic and/or optical interactions.

1.3.1 Radial sensitivity function and disturbances

Based on Fig. 3 the radial tracking error obtained from the radial optical sensor is described as follows:

$$\bar{x} \triangleq X_{ref} - x, \quad \dots (5)$$

Where x corresponds to the laser spot position driven by the radial controller, and X_{ref} stands for the track position signal that should be followed by the laser spot. The controlled signal x is computed as $x=L_R(s)\bar{x}$, where the transfer function $L_R(s)$ corresponds to the open loop transfer function $L_R(s)$ corresponds to the open loop transfer function given by the series connection between the radial actuator and the radial controller. Therefore, we have

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{1+Lr(s)} X_{ref}. \quad \dots (6)$$

The reference signal x_{ref} can be modeled as $x_{ref} = \bar{x}_{ref} + x_d$, where \bar{x}_{ref} corresponds to the nominal track location and x_d corresponds to the disturbance signal produced by the disc eccentricity. Since the nominal track location \bar{x}_{ref} has a very slow variation (generally a ramp signal during playback), the main problem concerns the minimization of the radial tracking error \bar{x} affected by the disturbance x_d , i.e. we are interested in minimizing the following sensitivity function

$$S_R \triangleq \bar{x}/x_d = \frac{1}{1+L(s)}. \quad \dots (7)$$

Due to the rotary nature of the opto-mechanical system, the disturbance signal x_d can be described by a sum of sinusoidal signals with frequencies multiple of the disc rotation frequency f_{rot} (e.g. $f_{rot} \in [20.5\text{Hz}, 50 \text{ Hz}]$ in the BD). Thus, if we assume that only the N^{th} -harmonic of this signal is relevant, the perturbation, in the time-domain, could be modeled as

$$X_d(t) = x_{d\max N} \cdot \sin(2\pi N f_{rot} t + \phi_{xN}), \quad \dots (8)$$

Where $x_{d\max N}$ stands for the maximal perturbation value (of the N^{th} -harmonic) and ϕ_{xN} stands for an unknown perturbation-signal phase (of the N^{th} -harmonic).

1.3.2 Focus sensitivity function and disturbances

Fig. 5 depicts a disc affected by disc tilt. Note that, at a given position of the laser spot, the servo tries to focus a pseudo-track (at the center of the spot) at the position \dot{z}_{ref} instead of the actual center of the track at the position z_{ref} . As a consequence, the focus tracking error measurement will be:

$$\bar{z} \triangleq \dot{z}_{ref} - z,$$

Fig. 5. Geometry of a disc affected by disc tilt (no scale).

Where the signal z corresponds to the vertical position of the laser spot driving by the focus controller. The controlled signal z is calculated as $z = L_f(s)\dot{z}$, where the transfer function given by the series connection between the focus actuator and the focus controller. Hence, the focus sensitivity function is:

$$S_F \triangleq \frac{\bar{z}}{z'_{ref}} = \frac{1}{1+L_f(s)} \quad \dots (10)$$

However, the signal \dot{z}_{ref} is not an exogenous input, i.e. the laser spot tries to focus a vertical reference that depends directly of the radial position x of the laser spot. From Fig. 5 we have

$$\dot{z}_{ref} = x \tan(\theta). \quad \dots (11)$$

The symbol θ stands for the inclination angle of the disc (i.e. the tilt angle). Therefore, assuming that θ varies slowly with respect to the x variations at high frequencies, and using the fact that $x = L_R(s)\bar{x}$, and \bar{x} given by (5), we have

$$\frac{\dot{z}_{ref}}{z_{ref}} = \frac{LR(s)}{\frac{1+LR(s)}{T_R}}, \quad \dots(12)$$

Where $z_{ref} = x_{ref} \tan\theta$ (see Fig. 5. Notice that Eq. (12) corresponds to the complementary sensitivity function of the radial servo, which we will denote as T_R . Therefore, substituting (12) into (10), the focus tracking error could be calculated as follows:

$$\dot{z} = \frac{LR(s)}{\frac{(1+LF(s))(1+LR(s))}{S_F T_R}} z_{ref}. \quad \dots (13)$$

The reference signal z_{ref} , is modelled as $z_{ref} = z^0_{ref} + z_d$, where z^0_{ref} corresponds to the nominal focus position (without presence of vertical deviations) and z_d corresponds to the disturbance signal produced by the disc tilt, wrapping or disc vibration. Then, the Eq. (12) could be rewritten as follows:

$$\frac{\dot{z}_d}{z_d} = \frac{LR(s)}{\frac{1+LR(s)}{T_R}}, \quad \dots(14)$$

Thus, we are interested in the following relationship:

$$\frac{\dot{z}}{z_d} = \frac{LR(s)}{(1+LF(s))(1+LR(s))} = S_F \cdot T_R, \quad \dots(15)$$

Where the signal z_d could be suitably modelled from Fig. 5 as follows:

$$Z_d(t) \triangleq \left(\frac{\dot{x}_{ref}}{x_{max}} \right) z_{dmax} \cdot \sin(2\pi N f_{rot} t + \phi_{zN}). \quad \dots(16)$$

X_{max} is the maximum radial position (defined in table 2) z_{dmaxN} the maximal vertical deviation at the Nth-harmonic, and f_{rot} the disc rotational frequency.

The coupled sensitivity function (15) is depicted in the Fig. 6. Note that the mechanical coupling effect appears as an amplification of the vertical disturbances around the middle frequencies (i.e. between 300 Hz and 30kHz). This effect can not be neglected, and the control design requires to reinforce attenuation at such frequencies.

1.4 Experimental validation

In order to validate the disturbance model proposed in Section 3, we make use of former experimental data obtained from an industrial optical disc servo control. Actually, the benchmark uses a DVD servo-mechanism at 1.5 times its reference linear speed, which emulates the behavior (in terms of disturbances

Fig. 6. Disturbance amplification (coupling effect) obtained from reference servos.

magnitudes and frequencies) of a BD working at its nominal speed (see Table 3). In our context we will use these obtained data to compute the disturbance magnitudes and the control tracking errors. The main objective is to try to evaluate the impact of the theoretical coupling effect on the performance of a given optical drive, and compare/validate the frequency regions where the disturbance amplification is present.

1.4.1 Set-up description

Fig. 7 depicts the employed set-up, where a digital signal analyzer (DSA) is used. The scheme includes both radial and vertical control loops as in Fig. 1. The available signals are: the controller output u , and the signal $(u+v)$ which corresponds to the actuator input. The signal v acts as an external excitation injected by the DSA into the loop. $C(s)$ is the actual controller and g_{opt} is the sensor (optical gain). In the sequel, we take $K(s) \triangleq C(s)g_{opt}$ as the controller.

The DSA sample frequency has been set in 12.8kHz; The measurement span covers from 1 Hz to 51.2kHz. Experiments were set with a sweep resolution of 100 points/sweep, the integration time 5 swept sine cycles, to have longer integration times at low frequencies, where the sweep sine cycles occurs slower. Four hundred resolution lines was considered, performed with 4 averaging per frequency point (RMS averaging mode), to reduce the measurement noise to its mean value.

Fig. 7. Experimental set-up including a digital signal analyzer.

The chosen injected swept sine was performed with an amplitude of 30mV_{pk} and a DC offset of 1 V, i.e. enough small injected signal in order to guarantee the “playability” property of the system during the test. That is, the tracking errors have to be small enough in such a way that the optical sensors continues to work inside their linear regions to avoid losing the radial seek action.

1.4.2 Computation of the sensitivities

In this section, it is assumed that the controllers and the plant models are well known. That is, we take average models of both the controller $K(s)$ and the servo-mechanism obtained during identification tests. The actuator model $G(s)$, including amplifiers, is described by a third order system, while the optical sensors were modeled as simple gains g_{opt} . The focus and radial controllers are lead-lag type controllers.

Therefore, the corresponding sensitivity functions magnitudes (in the frequency domain) are obtained by using the DSA, which computes the frequency response $\hat{S}_{ij}(\omega)$ by dividing the crossspectrum between the input and output by the power spectrum of the input. Eq. 17 indicates the equivalent relationship between the individual Fourier spectra, that is

$$|\hat{S}_{ij}(\omega)| \triangleq \frac{|[Uj+Vj](\omega)|}{|Vi(\omega)|} \quad \dots (17)$$

Where $U + V$ and V stand for the individual Fourier spectra of the signals $u + v$ and v , respectively. The indices i, j stand for the corresponding focus or radial loop (e.g. $I = F$ and $j = R$ or viceversa). This notation will be used in the sequel.

Here we are interested in obtaining cross sensitivity functions of the servomechanism. To this aim, we must to apply a stimulus signal in one of the loop (e.g. radial loop) and appreciate the effect on the second loop (e.g. focus loop), yielding

$$|\hat{S}_{ij}(\omega)| \triangleq \frac{|UF(\omega)|}{|VR(\omega)|} = \frac{kF}{1+KFGF} \frac{|zd(\omega)|}{|VR(\omega)|}, \quad \dots (18)$$

Where U_F is obtained from the scheme depicted in Fig. 7 for $V_F = 0$. That is, the only external signal injected into the focus loop comes from the vertical disturbance \dot{z}_d (see equations (14) and (16)). On the other hand, following a similar procedure for the radial loop we have:

$$|\hat{S}_{FR}(\omega)| \triangleq \frac{|UR(\omega)|}{|VF(\omega)|} = \frac{KR}{1+KRGR} \frac{|Xd(\omega)|}{|VF(\omega)|}, \quad \dots (19)$$

Where U_F is obtained from the scheme depicted in Fig. 7 for $V_R = 0$. Here, the only external repetitive (or periodical) disturbance x_d (see Eq. (8)). The left hand side of

Eqs. (18) and (19) are obtained from experiments, while the right hand ones are theoretical approximations of the expected sensitivity functions.

Therefore, it is clear that the frequency spectrum of disturbances \hat{z}_d and x_d can be estimated from Eqs. (18) and (19), respectively, as follows:

$$|\hat{Z}_d(\omega)| = \frac{1+KfGf}{Kf} |\hat{S}_{RF}(\omega)| \cdot |V_R(\omega)| \quad \dots(20)$$

$$|X_d(\omega)| = \frac{1+KrGr}{Kr} |\hat{S}_{FR}(\omega)| \cdot |V_F(\omega)| \quad \dots(21)$$

Fig. 8a illustrates the estimated disturbances obtained from the above equations. Note that the main disturbances, i.e. around the rotational disc frequency, represent the highest disturbances to attenuate (eccentricity and disc tilt). From Fig. 8b, also remark that the disturbances at middle and high frequencies are more relevant into the focus servo and the experimental values match well the theoretical disturbance model (Eq. 14). Remember that the coupling model (15) describes the frequency region where vertical disturbance will appear. In case of the radial servo, the most important disturbances are found, as expected, around the low frequencies. Notice in Fig. 8b, that the radial disturbances at middle frequencies could be neglected.

Fig. 8. (a) Estimated vertical $|Z_d(\omega)|$ (solid line) and radial disturbances $10 \times |X_d(\omega)|$ (dashed line); and (b) at zoom scale.

In order to estimate the impact on the performance of the drive, the focus and radial tracking errors could be estimated from (20) and (21) by substituting S_F and S_R from (10) and (7), respectively.

That is,

$$|\dot{Z}(\omega)| \triangleq S_F \cdot |\dot{Z}_d(\omega)| = \frac{1}{Kf} |\hat{S}_{RF}(\omega)| \cdot |V_R(\omega)|, \quad \dots(22)$$

$$|\dot{X}(\omega)| \triangleq S_R \cdot |X_d(\omega)| = \frac{1}{Kf} |\hat{S}_{RF}(\omega)| \cdot |V_R(\omega)|. \quad \dots(23)$$

The estimated tracking errors are plotted in Figs. 9a and b. Notice that for the radial servo, the desired performance (necessary attenuation of disturbances) is clearly met. Nevertheless, for the focus servo, there is an important sensitivity (with respect to disturbances) at middle and at high frequencies. Note that the magnitude of the focus tracking error \bar{z} is higher than that specified for DVD's. Infact, according to this result, the focus loop could work until the limit of the allowed deviation, e.g. less than 3 μm (i.e. into the linear region of sensors,

generally described by S-curves in optics, see for example, where the linear region is estimated to cover up to 6 μm peak to peak).

The optical gain g_{opt} is actually unknown, and this could produce inaccuracies in the plotted curves. Then, we may think that unmodeled sensor dynamics could change the measured value of the tracking errors. Nevertheless, the behavior and the magnitudes in the focus servo are manifestly enough for accepting that the proposed model match well the frequency regions where the total vertical disturbance appear. These results cannot be obtained in normal operation since disturbances are mainly at low frequencies; however, the results suggests the necessity to increase attenuation around middle frequencies to increase the robustness of the system.

1.5 Reducing the coupling effect by h^∞ control

In this section we will design independent robust controllers for focus and radial servos. To tackle the coupling effect problem, we will integrate the disturbance model, obtained in Section 3, into the h^∞ problem formulation to set a generic robust control problem.

1.5.1 Mixed-sensitivity h^∞ controller design

Recall that the h^∞ control problem is to find an input control $u_R = K_R(s)\bar{x}$ such that the radial sensitivity function of the controlled system (equivalently for the focus system) stay below a given reference curve (as it is depicted in Fig. 4). But, in addition, we require to minimize the coupling effect.

Third order actuator is sufficient to deal with control design subject to implementation constraints, e.g. for radial actuator we have,

$$G_R(s) = \frac{ke}{ml} \frac{1}{s^3 + \left(\frac{R}{L} + \frac{h}{m}\right)s^2 + \left(\frac{hR}{mL} + \frac{k}{m} + \frac{ke^2}{mL}\right)s + \frac{kR}{ml}} \quad \dots(24)$$

Where K_e , m , L , k , R and h correspond to the servo physical parameters. Similarly, we have an equivalent model for the focus actuator, denoted here as $G_F(s)$.

The Fig. 10 depicts the generic robust control problem for the radial loop. The functions W_1 and W_2 weight the controlled outputs y_1 and y_2 , and should be chosen

Fig. 10. The \mathcal{H}_∞ control problem scheme for the radial loop.

accordingly to the performance specifications. Moreover, the weighting function W_3 will incorporate the coupling model.

The generalized plant P (i.e. the interconnection of the plant and the weighting functions) is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} W_1 W_3 & -W_1 W_4 G_R & -W_1 G_R \\ 0 & 0 & W_2 \\ W_3 & -W_4 G_R & -G_R \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_{ref} \\ du \\ u_R \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots(25)$$

Thus, the h^∞ control problem is described as follows: Find a stabilizing controller $K_R(s)$ which minimize γ such that

$$\left\| \begin{pmatrix} W_1 W_3 S r & -W_1 W_4 S r G r \\ W_2 W_3 K r S r & -W_2 W_4 G r K r S r \end{pmatrix} \right\|_\infty < \gamma \quad \dots (26)$$

Remember that the obtained controller K_R has the same number of state variables as P . Then, the choice of the weighting functions is a key issue in the h^∞ control problem. Here, the repetitive disturbances should be attenuated in a particular frequency range. Then we will choose the weighting functions, for radial and focus design, as follows:

- (1) W_1 is used to impose a performance specification on S_R . That is,

$$W_1(s) = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{Ms}\right)^{s+wb}}{s+wb As}, \quad \dots(27)$$

Where $M_s = 1.0$ to introduce a margin of robustness limiting the peak of S_R , $w_b = 2\pi 250$ [rad/sec] to have a sensible attenuation of disturbances from low frequencies up to 250 Hz, and $A_s = 0.02$ to reduce the steady-state error.

(2) W_2 is aimed to respect the actuator limitations similar to the DVD. It is chosen as follows:

$$W_2(s) = \frac{s + (\frac{w_{bc}}{M_u})}{\epsilon s + w_{bc}}, \quad \dots(28)$$

Where $M_u = 1.5$ to impose limitations on the maximum value of the controller output signal up to 30 kHz, $w_{bc} = 2\pi 3 \times 10^3$ [rad/sec] to limit the effect of measurement noise and plant uncertainties at high frequencies, and $\epsilon = 0.01$ to ensure a high-frequency controller roll-off -40db/decade.

(3) W_3 (or disturbance model) is chosen as follows :

$$W_3 = 0.25, \quad \dots(29)$$

For radial control design, and

$$W_3(s) = 0.1 + / \cdot T_R(s), \quad \dots(30)$$

For focus control design (to incorporate the disturbance model). The constant $/$ allows to normalize (as an additional weight) the level of the vertical disturbances with respect to the radial ones (e.g. $/ = 0.5$).

W_4 is a constant. That is, $W_4 = 0.005$ for radial and $W_4 = 0.1$ for focus control design. All these values allow to obtain reasonable trade-off between control effort and disturbance attenuation.

Similarly, using the previous control design and the corresponding weighting function, the focus controller $K_F(s)$ for focus system $G_F(s)$ is obtained.

After computation, the minimal cost achieved for the radial control design was $\gamma = 0.286$, while the minimal cost achieved for the focus control design was $\gamma = 0.304$, these values mean that the obtained sensitivity functions match nearly the desired loop shaping. Fig. 11 illustrates the Bode magnitude of the obtained sensitivity functions. Remark that the radial sensitivity function S_R is less

conservative at low frequencies, and its bandwidth is much smaller than the theoretical reference servo dictated by the ECMA-standard.

Fig. 12 depicts the Bode magnitude of the designed h_∞ controllers. The order of the desired h_∞ controllers are equal to 8th (after use a reduced 3th order disturbance model T_R). The controller order could be reduced before implementation, i.e. taking into account actual industrial constraints.

Thus, the amplification due to the coupling effect has been reduced, and the system performance is improved at middle frequencies, all that respecting the actuators constraints. Fig. 11b and c illustrate the sensitivity function related to the control effort.

1.5.2 Simulation results using experimental data

The performance of the h_∞ controller is here evaluated under the presence of disturbances. For simulations, we use the estimated disturbances. Fig. 13a illustrates the disturbance attenuation achieved by using the robust controller. Notice that we can achieve more robust focus servo. In the case of the BD servos, this aspect becomes a key issue. On the other hand, the disturbance attenuation in the radial servo is lower for the robust controller. This is not a surprise, because we reduce the radial servo bandwidth to contribute to compensate the coupling effect. Nevertheless, the experimental results show that these frequency bounds are quite conservative, in the radial case, and the track spectrum is well below them.

Major improvements could be obtained by taken into account other particular solutions. For example, the proposed controller can be improved by adding a repetitive control (i.e. a memory-loop term). In this way, the memory-loop term will be designed for attenuation of well known repetitive disturbances (at low frequency for example), while the proposed h_∞ controller will be designed to achieve robustness for such disturbances (i.e. for changes in the period time of disturbances) and, in addition, for attenuation of the coupling effect (at middle and high frequencies).

Fig. 11 (a) Sensitivity functions S . (b) Sensitivity Functions KS , (c) Sensitivity functions GKS and (d) Sensitivity functions SG .

Fig. 12. Frequency response of focus and radial controllers $C(s)$, i.e. without taking into account the optical gains.

Fig. 13. Tracking error estimations of the compensated servo: (a) focus and (b) radial.

1.5.3 Uncertainty modeling and robustness analysis

The nominal model, used for control design, is obtained for considering the average values of physical parameters of several industrial pick-up's. The stability and the performance of the modeled system is guaranteed by using a suitable robust controller. However, in practice, there is always a mismatch between the model and the system to be controlled. In the case of the mass production of Blu-ray disc players, the manufacturing tolerances should be increased in order to reduce production costs. As a consequence, the designed controller will be implemented in a wide set of pick-ups, that differ of the average model. Here, we are interested to evaluate the stability and the performance of the whole set of possible real servo-mechanisms. The whole set of systems is modeled as the average model subject to parametric uncertainties. Table 4 encloses several physical parameters of the nominal radial actuator together with their percentage of variations.

Notice the high uncertainty of the parameter L (inductance) and K_e (electromagnetic constant). We will take into account these parameters in order to build an uncertain model enough accuracy for robust analysis.

1.5.4 Uncertain modeling

The following actuator model (radial or focus servo) described by the following electrical and mechanical systems:

$$L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + Ri(t) = \Delta_E \cdot [v(t) - K_e \frac{dx(t)}{dt}] \quad \dots(31)$$

$$m \frac{d^2(t)}{dt^2} + h \frac{dx(t)}{dt} + kx(t) = \Delta_M \cdot K_e i(t) \quad \dots(32)$$

Where Δ_E and Δ_M globalize the electrical and mechanical parameteric uncertainties, respectively. For example, the nominal model could be obtained for fixing $\Delta_E = \Delta_M = 1$. It is easy to see that the uncertain actuator model could be described by the following transfer function ($i = R, F$, radial or focus actuator):

$$G_i(s) \triangleq \frac{X(s)}{V(s)} = \frac{ke\Delta E m}{c_1 s^3 + c_2 s^2 + (c_3 + K^2 e \Delta E m) + c_4} \quad \dots(33)$$

The constants c 's are calculated from the physical parameters described in Table 4, and the uncertain parameter Δ_{Em} is defined as follows: $\Delta_{Em} \triangleq \Delta_E \cdot \Delta_M$.

This uncertain model could be very conservative, but permits to analyze a system respecting the physical constraints between the electrical and mechanical elements, for example the electromagnetic constant K_e which couples both subsystems. In addition, in practical situations it is very difficult to estimate the value of the independent parameters because much of them are strongly related (e.g. L/R). Fig. 14 depicts the relative plant errors of 250 random servo parametric combinations.

Table 4
Radial actuator parameters variation. Source [3].

Parameter		Nominal value	% of variation
Resistance of coil	$R[\Omega]$	4.83	15
Inductance of coil	$L[\mu H]$	12	33
Electromagnetic constant	$K_e[Wb/m]$	0.1212	26
Moving mass	$m[g]$	0.30	10
Damping factor	$h[Ns/m]$	0.0160	15
Elastic constant	$k[N/m]$	45.35	20

Fig. 14. Relative plant errors $\left| \frac{G_A(s) - G(s)}{G(s)} \right|$, of 250 random parametric combinations.

Fig. 15. Singular values μ for (a) radial servo, and (b) focus servo.

Table 5

Robust stability and performance margins for radial servo.

Parameter	%	% Robust stability	% Robust performance
K_e	± 26	± 53	± 37
Δ_{EM}	± 25	± 50	± 35

Table 6

Robust stability and performance margins for focus servo.

Parameter	%	% Robust stability	% Robust performance
K_e	± 26	± 53	± 34
Δ_{EM}	± 25	± 50	± 33

Fig. 16. Robust reduction of the coupling effect for 250 combinations of focus and radial servos.

1.5.5 Robust stability and performance analysis

The controlled system can be analyzed using the μ -analysis. The structured singular value is, in the case of Robust stability analysis, a measure of how big a perturbation to a system must be in order to make the closed-loop system unstable, or in the case of Robust performance analysis, a measure of how big a perturbation to a system can be to assure the desired closed loop performance. For the case of optical disc drives system, we are particularly concerned with the robustness (stability and performance) of the closed system with respect to variations in two global parameters (K_e and Δ_{Em}). In the robust stability analysis framework, model uncertainties are represented using linear fractional transformations. The uncertain continuous system is described by 3 states, 1 output, 1 input, with nominal $K_e = 0.1221$, +/- 26%, 3 occurrences, and nominal $\Delta_{Em} = 1$, +/- 25%, 2 occurrences. Fig. 15 illustrates the achieved singular values μ for radial and focus servos. Table 5 and 6 summarizes the obtained robustness margins.

Remark that even using a conservative uncertain model the stability and the performance of the controlled set of systems are guaranteed for important variations in the nominal parameters, as illustrates the Fig. 15. As expected, the performance is guaranteed for smaller variations of parameters, but it is still a considerable allowed variation. This point is very important since the linear model of the drive is only valid as long as the optical detectors are in linear region that is actually very tight, robust performance is highly necessary for guaranteeing the stability of the system.

To evaluate the impact of the parameter variation in the achieved coupling effect, that is not clearly observed into the robust analysis. Fig 16 illustrates the expected coupling effect should be bounded by a unit gain, which is an admissible value for “playability”. Thus, the proposed controllers are quite robust with respect to the obtained ones from the reference servos (see Fig. 6) and those obtained from the current industrial controllers (see also Fig. 9a).

1.6 Conclusion

In this project a disturbance model for BD servomechanisms has been validated under experimental data and a suitable robust h_{∞} controller has been designed. The control design process takes into account the disturbance model for the purpose of reducing the coupling effect.

The proposed disturbance model describes the opto-mechanical coupling between, the independent-designed, radial and the vertical control loops in Optical Disc Drives. The main result concerns the fact that the coupling effect appears as an amplification of the vertical disturbances around the middle and the high frequencies in the vertical control loop. The proposed coupling model has been validated by using experimental data. It is found that the model is enough accurate to describe the coupling behavior, and it could be useful for high-bandwidth controller design.

In terms of control, the proposed robust controllers are able to compensate the coupling effect, thanks to the fact that the disturbance model is used into the h_{∞} control problem formulation. The obtained radial controller is less conservative at very low frequencies, using lower bandwidth control. However, this fact permits to suitably attenuate the coupling effect by using a higher bandwidth focus controller. A robust stability and performance analysis has been done yielding considerable margins of stability and performance of the parametric uncertain BD model. This is quite promising in mass-production in BD drives.

The achieved attenuation of the coupling effect aims to guarantee the playability of the low quality media, contributing to reduce drives and disc production costs.

2. How Laser works?

2.0 Introduction

Star Wars," "Star Trek," "Battlestar Galactica" -- laser technology plays a pivotal role in science fiction movies and books. It's no doubt thanks to these sorts of stories that we now associate lasers with futuristic warfare and sleek spaceships.

But lasers play a pivotal role in our everyday lives, too. The fact is that they show up in an amazing range of products and technologies. You'll find them in everything from CD players to dental drills to high-speed metal cutting machines to measuring systems. Tattoo removal, hair replacement, eye surgery -- they all use lasers. But what is a laser? What makes a laser beam different from the beam of a flashlight? Specifically, what makes a laser light different from other kinds of light? How are lasers classified?

2.1 The Basics of an Atom

There are only about 100 different kinds of atoms in the entire universe. Everything we see is made up of these 100 atoms in an unlimited number of combinations. How these atoms are arranged and bonded together determines whether the atoms make up a cup of water, a piece of metal, or the fizz that comes out of your soda can!

Atoms are constantly in motion. They continuously vibrate, move and rotate. Even the atoms that make up the chairs that we sit in are moving around. Solids are actually in motion! Atoms can be in different states of excitation. In other words, they can have different energies. If we apply a lot of energy to an atom, it can leave what is called the ground-state energy level and go to an excited level. The level of excitation depends on the amount of energy that is applied to the atom via heat, light, or electricity.

Here is a classic interpretation of what the atom looks like:

An atom, in the simplest model, consists of a nucleus and orbiting electrons

This simple atom consists of a **nucleus** (containing the protons and neutrons) and an **electron cloud**. It's helpful to think of the electrons in this cloud circling the **nucleus** in many different orbits

2.2 Absorbing Energy

Although more modern views of the atom do not depict discrete orbits for the electrons, it can be useful to think of these orbits as the different energy levels of the atom. In other words, if we apply some heat to an atom, we might expect that some of the electrons in the lower-energy orbitals would transition to higher-energy orbital's farther away from the nucleus.

Absorption of energy:

An atom absorbs energy in the form of heat, light, or electricity. Electrons may move from a lower-energy orbit to a higher-energy orbit

This is a highly simplified view of things, but it actually reflects the core idea of how atoms work in terms of lasers.

Once an electron moves to a higher-energy orbit, it eventually wants to return to the ground state. When it does, it releases its energy as a photon -- a particle of light. You see atoms releasing energy as photons all the time. For example, when the heating element in a toaster turns bright red, the red color is caused by atoms, excited by heat, releasing red photons. When you see a picture on a TV screen, what you are seeing is phosphor atoms, excited by high-speed electrons, emitting different colors of light. Anything that produces light -- fluorescent lights, gas lanterns, incandescent bulbs -- does it through the action of electrons changing orbits and releasing photons.

2.3 The Laser/Atom Connection

A laser is a device that controls the way that energized atoms release photons. "Laser" is an acronym for light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation, which describes very succinctly how a laser works.

Although there are many types of lasers, all have certain essential features. In a laser, the lasing medium is "pumped" to get the atoms into an excited state. Typically, very intense flashes of light or electrical discharges pump the lasing medium and create a large collection of excited-state atoms (atoms with higher-energy electrons). It is necessary to have a large collection of atoms in the excited state for the laser to work efficiently. In general, the atoms are excited to a level

that is two or three levels above the ground state. This increases the degree of population inversion. The population inversion is the number of atoms in the excited state versus the number in ground state.

Once the lasing medium is pumped, it contains a collection of atoms with some electrons sitting in excited levels. The excited electrons have energies greater than the more relaxed electrons. Just as the electron absorbed some amount of energy to reach this excited level, it can also release this energy. As the figure below illustrates, the electron can simply relax, and in turn rid itself of some energy. This emitted energy comes in the form of photons (light energy). The photon emitted has a very specific wavelength (color) that depends on the state of the electron's energy when the photon is released. Two identical atoms with electrons in identical states will release photons with identical wavelengths

2.4 Properties of Laser Light

Laser light is very different from normal light. Laser light has the following properties:

The light released is monochromatic. It contains one specific wavelength of light (one specific color). The wavelength of light is determined by the amount of energy released when the electron drops to a lower orbit.

The light released is coherent. It is “organized” -- each photon moves in step with the others. This means that all of the photons have wave fronts that launch in unison.

The light is very directional. A laser light has a very tight beam and is very strong and concentrated. A flashlight, on the other hand, releases light in many directions, and the light is very weak and diffuse.

To make these three properties occur takes something called stimulated emission. This does not occur in your ordinary flashlight -- in a flashlight, all of the atoms release their photons randomly. In stimulated emission, photon emission is organized.

The photon that any atom releases has a certain wavelength that is dependent on the energy difference between the excited state and the ground state. If this photon (possessing a certain energy and phase) should encounter another atom that has an electron in the same excited state, stimulated emission can occur. The first photon can stimulate or induce atomic emission such that the subsequent emitted photon (from the second atom) vibrates with the same frequency and direction as the incoming photon.

The other key to a laser is a pair of mirrors, one at each end of the lasing medium. Photons, with a very specific wavelength and phase, reflect off the mirrors to travel back and forth through the lasing medium. In the process, they stimulate other electrons to make the downward energy jump and can cause the emission of more photons of the same wavelength and phase. A cascade effect occurs, and soon we have propagated many, many photons of the same wavelength and phase. The mirror at one end of the laser is "half-silvered," meaning it reflects some light and lets some light through. The light that makes it through is the laser light.

2.5 Ruby Lasers

A ruby laser consists of a flash tube (like you would have on a camera), a ruby rod and two mirrors (one half-silvered). The ruby rod is the lasing medium and the flash tube pumps it.

1. The laser in its non-lasing state

2. The flash tube fires and injects light into the ruby rod. The light excites atoms in the ruby.

3. Some of these atoms emit photons.

4. Some of these photons run in a direction parallel to the ruby's axis, so they bounce back and forth off the mirrors. As they pass through the crystal, they stimulate emission in other atoms

5. Monochromatic, single-phase, collimated light leaves the ruby through the half-silvered mirror -- laser light!

2.6 Laser Classifications

Lasers are classified into four broad areas depending on the potential for causing biological damage.

Class I - These lasers cannot emit laser radiation at known hazard levels.

Class I.A. - This is a special designation that applies only to lasers that are "not intended for viewing," such as a supermarket laser scanner. The upper power limit of Class I.A. is 4.0 mW.

Class II - These are low-power visible lasers that emit above Class I levels but at a radiant power not above 1 mW. The concept is that the human aversion reaction to bright light will protect a person.

Class IIIA - These are intermediate-power lasers (cw: 1-5 mW), which are hazardous only for intra beam viewing. Most pen-like pointing lasers are in this class.

Class IIIB - These are moderate-power lasers.

Class IV - These are high-power lasers (cw: 500 mW, pulsed: 10 J/cm² or the diffuse reflection limit), which are hazardous to view under any condition (directly or diffusely scattered), and are a potential fire hazard and a skin hazard. Significant controls are required of Class IV laser facilities.

This is a list of laser types, their operational wavelengths, and their applications. Many thousands of kinds of laser are known, but most of them are not used beyond specialized research.

2.6.1 Gas lasers

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Helium-neon laser	632.8 nm (543.5 nm, 593.9 nm, 611.8 nm, 1.1523 μm , 1.52 μm , 3.3913 μm)	Electrical discharge	Interferometer, holography, spectroscopy, barcode scanning, alignment, optical demonstrations.
Argon laser	454.6 nm, 488.0 nm, 514.5 nm (351 nm, 363.8, 457.9 nm, 465.8 nm, 476.5 nm, 472.7 nm, 528.7 nm, also frequency doubled to provide 244 nm, 257 nm)	Electrical discharge	Retinal phototherapy (for diabetes), lithography, confocal microscopy, spectroscopy pumping other lasers.
Krypton laser	416 nm, 530.9 nm, 568.2 nm, 647.1 nm, 676.4 nm, 752.5 nm, 799.3 nm	Electrical discharge	Scientific research, mixed with argon to create "white-light" lasers, light shows.
Xenon ion laser	Many lines throughout visible spectrum extending into the UV and IR.	Electrical discharge	Scientific research.
Nitrogen laser	337.1 nm	Electrical discharge	Pumping of dye lasers, measuring air pollution, scientific research.

			Nitrogen lasers can operate superradiantly (without a resonator cavity). Amateur laser construction. See TEA laser
Carbon dioxide laser	10.6 μm , (9.4 μm)	Transverse (high power) or longitudinal (low power) electrical discharge	Material processing (cutting, welding, etc.), surgery.
Carbon monoxide laser	2.6 to 4 μm , 4.8 to 8.3 μm	Electrical discharge	Material processing (engraving, welding, etc.), photoacoustic spectroscopy.
Excimer laser	193 nm (ArF), 248 nm (KrF), 308 nm (XeCl), 353 nm (XeF)	Excimer recombination via electrical discharge	Ultraviolet lithography for semiconductor manufacturing, laser surgery, LASIK.

2.6.2 Chemical lasers

Used as directed-energy weapons.

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Hydrogen fluoride laser	2.7 to 2.9 μm for Hydrogen fluoride (<80% Atmospheric transmittance)	Chemical reaction in a burning jet of ethylene and nitrogen trifluoride (NF_3)	Used in research for laser weaponry by the U.S. DOD, operated in continuous wave mode, can have power in the

Deuterium fluoride laser	~3800 nm (3.6 to 4.2 μm) (~90% Atm. transmittance)	chemical reaction	megawatt range. MIRACL, Pulsed Energy Projectile & Tactical High Energy Laser
COIL (Chemical oxygen-iodine laser)	1.315 μm (<70% Atmospheric transmittance)	Chemical reaction in a jet of singlet delta oxygen and iodine	Laser weaponry, scientific and materials research, laser used in the U.S. military's Airborne laser, operated in continuous wave mode, can have power in the megawatt range.
Agil (All gas-phase iodine laser)	1.315 μm (<70% Atmospheric transmittance)	Chemical reaction of chlorine atoms with gaseous hydrazoic acid, resulting in excited molecules of nitrogen chloride, which then pass their energy to the iodine atoms.	Scientific, weaponry, aerospace.

2.6.3 Dye lasers

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Dye lasers	390-435 nm (stilbene), 460-515 nm (coumarin 102), 570-640 nm	Other laser, flashlamp	Research, spectroscopy, birthmark removal, isotope separation. The tuning range of

(rhodamine 6G), many others

the laser depends on which dye is used.

2.6.4 Metal-vapor lasers

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Helium-cadmium (HeCd) metal-vapor laser	441.563 nm, 325 nm		Printing and typesetting applications, fluorescence excitation examination (ie. in U.S. paper currency printing), and scientific research.
Helium-mercury (HeHg) metal-vapor laser	567 nm, 615 nm	Electrical discharge in metal vapor mixed with helium buffer gas.	Rare, scientific research, amateur laser construction.
Helium-selenium (HeSe) metal-vapor laser	up to 24 wavelengths between red and UV		Rare, scientific research, amateur laser construction.
Helium-silver (HeAg) metal-vapor laser	224.3		Scientific research
Neon-copper (NeCu) metal-vapor laser	248.6	Electrical discharge in metal vapor mixed with neon	Scientific research

Copper vapor laser	510.6 nm, 578.2 nm	buffer gas. Electrical discharge	Dermatological uses, high speed photography, pump for dye lasers.
Gold vapor laser	627 nm		Rare, dermatological and photodynamic therapy uses.

2.6.5 Solid-state lasers

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Ruby laser	694.3 nm	Flashlamp	Holography, tattoo removal. The first type of visible light laser invented; May 1960.
Nd:YAG laser	1.064 μm , (1.32 μm)	Flashlamp, laser diode	Material processing, rangefinding, laser target designation, surgery, research, pumping other lasers (combined with frequency doubling to produce a green 532 nm beam). One of the most common high power lasers. Usually pulsed (down to fractions of a nanosecond)
Er: YAG laser	2.94 μm	Flashlamp, laser diode	Periodontal scaling, Dentistry
Neodymium YLF (Nd: YLF) solid-state laser	1.047 and 1.053 μm	Flashlamp, laser diode	Mostly used for pulsed pumping of certain types of pulsed Ti: sapphire lasers, combined with frequency

Neodymium doped
Yttrium
orthovanadate
(Nd:YVO₄) laser

1.064 μm

laser diode

Neodymium doped
yttrium calcium
oxoborate
Nd:YCa₄O(BO₃)₃ or
simply Nd:YCOB

~1.060 μm
(~530 nm at
second
harmonic)

laser diode

Neodymium glass
(Nd:Glass) laser

~1.062 μm
(Silicate
glasses),
~1.054 μm
(Phosphate
glasses)

Flashlamp,
laser diode

Titanium sapphire
(Ti: sapphire) laser

650-1100 nm

Other laser

doubling.

Mostly used for continuous pumping of mode-locked Ti:sapphire or dye lasers, in combination with frequency doubling. Also used pulsed for marking and micromachining. A frequency doubled Nd:YVO₄ laser is also the normal way of making a green laser pointer.

Nd:YCOB is a so called "self-frequency doubling" or SFD laser material which is both capable of lasing and which has nonlinear characteristics suitable for second harmonic generation. Such materials have the potential to simplify the design of high brightness green lasers.

Used in extremely high power (terawatt scale), high energy (mega joules) multiple beam systems for inertial confinement fusion. Nd: Glass lasers are usually frequency tripled to the third harmonic at 351 nm in laser fusion devices.

Spectroscopy, LIDAR, research. This material is often used in highly-tunable mode-

			locked infrared lasers to produce ultra short pulses and in amplifier lasers to produce ultrashort and ultra-intense pulses.
Thulium YAG (Tm:YAG) laser	2.0 μm	Laser diode	LIDAR.
Ytterbium YAG (Yb:YAG) laser	1.03 μm	Laser diode, flashlamp	Optical refrigeration, materials processing, ultrashort pulse research, multiphoton microscopy, LIDAR.
Ytterbium: $_2\text{O}_3$ (glass or ceramics) laser	1.03 μm	Laser diode	Ultra short pulse research.
Ytterbium doped glass laser (rod, plate/chip, and fiber)	1. μm	Laser diode.	Fiber version is capable of producing several-kilowatt continuous power, having ~70-80% optical-to-optical and ~25% electrical-to-optical efficiency. Material processing: cutting, welding, marking; nonlinear fiber optics: broadband fiber-nonlinearity based sources, pump for fiber Raman lasers; distributed Raman amplification pump for telecommunications.
Holmium YAG (Ho:YAG) laser	2.1 μm	Laser diode	Tissue ablation, kidney stone removal, dentistry.

Cerium doped lithium strontium(or calcium) aluminum fluoride (Ce:LiSAF, Ce:LiCAF)	~280 to 316 nm	Frequency quadrupled Nd:YAG laser pumped, excimer laser pumped, copper vapor laser pumped.	Remote atmospheric sensing, LIDAR, optics research.
Promethium 147 doped phosphate glass (¹⁴⁷ Pm ³⁺ :Glass) solid-state laser	933 nm, 1098 nm	??	Laser material is radioactive. Once demonstrated in use at LLNL in 1987, room temperature 4 level lasing in ¹⁴⁷ Pm doped into a lead-indium-phosphate glass étalon.
Chromium doped chrysoberyl (alexandrite) laser	Typically tuned in the range of 700 to 820 nm	Flashlamp, laser diode, mercury arc (for CW mode operation)	Dermatological uses, LIDAR, laser machining.
Erbium doped and erbium-ytterbium codoped glass lasers	1.53-1.56 μm	Laser diode	These are made in rod, plate/chip, and optical fiber form. Erbium doped fibers are commonly used as optical amplifiers for telecommunications.
Trivalent uranium doped calcium fluoride (U:CaF ₂) solid-state laser	2.5 μm	Flashlamp	First 4-level solid state laser (November 1960) developed by Peter Sorokin and Mirek Stevenson at IBM research labs, second laser invented overall (after Maiman's ruby laser), liquid helium cooled,

Divalent samarium doped calcium fluoride (Sm:CaF ₂) laser	708.5 nm	Flashlamp	unused today. [1] Also invented by Peter Sorokin and Mirek Stevenson at IBM research labs, early 1961. Liquid helium cooled, unused today. [2]
F-center laser.	2.3-3.3 μm	Ion laser	Spectroscopy

2.6.6 Semiconductor lasers

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Semiconductor laser diode (general information)	0.4-20 μm, depending on active region material.		Telecommunications, holography, printing, weapons, machining, welding, pump sources for other lasers.
GaN	0.4 μm		Optical discs.
AlGaAs	0.63-0.9 μm	Electrical current	Optical discs, laser pointers, data communications. 780 nm Compact Disc player laser is the most common laser type in the world. Solid-state laser pumping, machining, medical.
InGaAsP	1.0-2.1 μm		Telecommunications, solid-state laser pumping, machining, medical.
lead salt	3-20 μm		
Vertical cavity surface emitting	850 - 1500 nm, depending on		Telecommunications

laser (VCSEL)	material	
Quantum cascade laser	Mid-infrared to far-infrared.	Research, Future applications may include collision-avoidance radar, industrial-process control and medical diagnostics such as breath analyzers.
Hybrid silicon laser	Mid-infrared	Research

2.6.7 Other types of lasers

Laser gain medium and type	Operation wavelength(s)	Pump source	Applications and notes
Free electron laser	A broad wavelength range (about 100 nm - several mm); one relativistic free electron laser may be tunable over a wavelength range	electron beam	Atmospheric research, material science, medical applications.
Gas dynamic laser	Several lines around 10.5 um; other frequencies may be possible with different gas mixtures	Spin state population inversion in carbon dioxide molecules caused by supersonic adiabatic expansion of mixture of	Military applications; can operate in CW mode at several megawatts optical power.

		nitrogen and carbon dioxide	
"Nickel-like" Samarium laser	X-rays at 7.3 nm wavelength	Lasing in ultra-hot samarium plasma formed by double pulse terawatt scale irradiation fluences created by Rutherford Appleton Laboratory's Nd:glass Vulcan laser.	First demonstration of efficient "saturated" operation of a sub-10 nm X-ray laser, possible applications in high resolution microscopy and holography, operation is close to the "water window" at 2.2 to 4.4 nm where observation of DNA structure and the action of viruses and drugs on cells can be examined.
Raman laser, uses inelastic stimulated Raman scattering in a nonlinear media, mostly fiber, for amplification	1-2 μm for fiber version	Other laser, mostly Yb-glass fiber lasers	Complete 1-2 μm wavelength coverage; distributed optical signal amplification for telecommunications; optical solitons generation and amplification
Nuclear pumped laser	See gas lasers	Nuclear fission	Research

3. How does CD work?

3.0 Introduction

CDs and DVDs are everywhere these days. Whether they are used to hold music, data or computer software, they have become the standard medium for distributing large quantities of information in a reliable package. Compact discs are so easy and cheap to produce that America Online sends out millions of them every year to entice new users. And if you have a computer and CD-R drive, you can create your own CDs, including any information you want.

3.1 Understanding the CD: Material

A CD can store up to 74 minutes of music, so the total amount of digital data that must be stored on a CD is:

$$44,100 \text{ samples/channel/second} \times 2 \text{ bytes/sample} \times 2 \text{ channels} \times 74 \text{ minutes} \times 60 \text{ seconds/minute} = 783,216,000 \text{ bytes}$$

To fit more than 783 megabytes (MB) onto a disc only 4.8 inches (12 cm) in diameter requires that the individual bytes be very small. By examining the physical construction of a CD, you can begin to understand just how small these bytes are.

A CD is a fairly simple piece of plastic, about four one-hundredths ($4/100$) of an inch (1.2 mm) thick. Most of a CD consists of an injection-molded piece of clear polycarbonate plastic. During manufacturing, this plastic is impressed with microscopic bumps arranged as a single, continuous, extremely long spiral track of data. We'll return to the bumps in a moment. Once the clear piece of polycarbonate is formed, a thin, reflective aluminum layer is sputtered onto the disc, covering the bumps. Then a thin acrylic layer is sprayed over the aluminum to protect it. The label is then printed onto the acrylic. A cross section of a complete CD (not to scale) looks like this:

Cross-section of a CD

3.1.1 Understanding the CD: The Spiral

A CD has a single spiral track of data, circling from the inside of the disc to the outside. The fact that the spiral track starts at the center means that the CD can be smaller than 4.8 inches (12 cm) if desired, and in fact there are now plastic baseball cards and business cards that you can put in a CD player. CD business cards hold about 2 MB of data before the size and shape of the card cuts off the spiral.

What the picture on the right does not even begin to impress upon you is how incredibly small the data track is -- it is approximately 0.5 microns wide, with 1.6 microns separating one track from the next. (A micron is a millionth of a meter.) And the bumps are even more miniscule.

3.1.2 Understanding the CD: Bumps

The elongated bumps that make up the track are each 0.5 microns wide, a minimum of 0.83 microns long and 125 nanometers high. (A nanometer is a billionth of a meter.) Looking through the polycarbonate layer at the bumps, they look something like this:

You will often read about "pits" on a CD instead of bumps. They appear as pits on the aluminum side, but on the side the laser reads from, they are bumps.

The incredibly small dimensions of the bumps make the spiral track on a CD extremely long. If you could lift the data track off a CD and stretch it out into a straight line, it would be 0.5 microns wide and almost 3.5 miles (5 km) long.

3.2 CD player Components

The CD player has the job of finding and reading the data stored as bumps on the CD. Considering how small the bumps are, the CD player is an exceptionally precise piece of equipment. The drive consists of three fundamental components:

A **drive motor** spins the disc. This drive motor is precisely controlled to rotate between 200 and 500 rpm depending on which track is being read.

A **laser** and a **lens system** focus in on and read the bumps.

A **tracking mechanism** moves the laser assembly so that the laser's beam can follow the spiral track. The tracking system has to be able to move the laser at micron resolutions.

Inside a CD player

4. How does DVDs work?

4.0 Introduction

It wasn't really that long ago that VHS tapes dominated the home video market, but now, DVDs have all but wiped them out completely. Going from tape to disc gave the home theater experience a major upgrade, and ushered in an era of feature-packed special edition home video.

4.1 DVD Disks

A DVD is very similar to a CD, but it has a much **larger data capacity**. A standard DVD holds about seven times more data than a CD does. This huge capacity means that a DVD has enough room to store a full-length, MPEG-2-encoded movie, as well as a lot of other information.

DVD Fact

The first DVD player hit the market in March 1997.

Here are the typical contents of a DVD movie:

- Up to 133 minutes of high-resolution video, in letterbox or pan-and-scan format, with 720 dots of horizontal resolution (The video compression ratio is typically 40:1 using MPEG-2 compression.)
- Soundtrack presented in up to eight languages using 5.1 channel Dolby digital surround sound
- Subtitles in up to 32 languages
- DVD can also be used to store almost eight hours of CD-quality music per side.

The format offers many advantages over VHS tapes:

- DVD picture quality is better, and many DVDs have Dolby Digital or DTS sound, which is much closer to the sound you experience in a movie theater.
- Many DVD movies have an on-screen index, where the creator of the DVD has labeled many of the significant parts of the movie, sometimes with a picture. With your remote, if you select the part of the movie you want to

view, the DVD player will take you right to that part, with no need to rewind or fast-forward.

- DVD players are compatible with audio CDs.
- Some DVD movies have both the letterbox format, which fits wide-screen TVs, and the standard TV size format, so you can choose which way you want to watch the movie.
- DVD movies may have several soundtracks on them, and they may provide subtitles in different languages. Foreign movies may give you the choice between the version dubbed into your language, or the original soundtrack with subtitles in your language.

4.2 DVD Layers

DVDs are of the same diameter and thickness as CDs, and they are made using some of the same materials and manufacturing methods. Like a CD, the data on a DVD is encoded in the form of small pits and bumps in the track of the disc.

A DVD is composed of several layers of plastic, totaling about 1.2 millimeters thick. Each layer is created by injection molding polycarbonate plastic. This process forms a disc that has microscopic bumps arranged as a single, continuous and extremely long spiral track of data. More on the bumps later.

Once the clear pieces of polycarbonate are formed, a thin reflective layer is sputtered onto the disc, covering the bumps. Aluminum is used behind the inner layers, but a semi-reflective gold layer is used for the outer layers, allowing the laser to focus through the outer and onto the inner layers. After all of the layers are made, each one is coated with lacquer, squeezed together and cured under infrared light. For single-sided discs, the label is silk-screened onto the non-readable side. Double-sided discs are printed only on the non-readable area near the hole in the middle. Cross sections of the various types of completed DVDs (not to scale) look like this:

Single-sided, single layer (4.7GB)

Single-sided, double layer (8.5GB)

Double-sided, double layer (17GB)

©2000 How Stuff Works

DVD formats

Each writable layer of a DVD has a spiral track of data. On single-layer DVDs, the track always circles from the inside of the disc to the outside. That the spiral track starts at the center means that a single-layer DVD can be smaller than 12 centimeters if desired.

What the image to the right cannot impress upon you is how incredibly tiny the data track is -- just 740 nanometers separate one track from the next (a nanometer is a billionth of a meter). And the elongated bumps that make up the track are each 320 nanometers wide, a minimum of 400 nanometers long and 120 nanometers high. The following figure illustrates looking through the polycarbonate layer at the bumps.

©2000 How Stuff Works

Data tracks on a DVD

DVD pit layout

You will often read about "pits" on a DVD instead of bumps. They appear as pits on the aluminum side, but on the side that the laser reads from, they are bumps.

The microscopic dimensions of the bumps make the spiral track on a DVD extremely long. If you could lift the data track off a single layer of a DVD, and stretch it out into a straight line, it would be almost **7.5 miles** long! That means that a double-sided, double-layer DVD would have **30 miles** (48 km) of data!

To read bumps this small you need an incredibly precise disc-reading mechanism.

4.3 DVD Storage Capacities

DVDs can store more data than CDs for a few reasons:

- Higher-density data storage
- Less overhead, more area
- Multi-layer storage

4.3.1 Higher Density Data Storage

Single-sided, single-layer DVDs can store about seven times more data than CDs. A large part of this increase comes from the pits and tracks being smaller on DVDs.

Specification	CD	DVD
Track Pitch	1600 nanometers	740 nanometers
Minimum Pit Length (single-layer DVD)	830 nanometers	400 nanometers
Minimum Pit Length (double-layer DVD)	830 nanometers	440 nanometers

Let's try to get an idea of how much more data can be stored due to the physically tighter spacing of pits on a DVD. The track pitch on a DVD is 2.16 times smaller, and the minimum pit length for a single-layer DVD is 2.08 times smaller than on a CD. By multiplying these two numbers, we find that there is room for about 4.5 times as many pits on a DVD. So where does the rest of the increase come from?

4.3.2 Less Overhead, More Area

On a CD, there is a lot of extra information encoded on the disc to allow for error correction -- this information is really just a repetition of information that is already on the disc. The error correction scheme that a CD uses is quite old and inefficient compared to the method used on DVDs. The DVD format doesn't waste as much space on error correction, enabling it to store much more real information.

Another way that DVDs achieve higher capacity is by encoding data onto a slightly larger area of the disc than is done on a CD.

4.3.3 Multi-Layer Storage

To increase the storage capacity even more, a DVD can have up to four layers, two on each side. The laser that reads the disc can actually focus on the second layer through the first layer. Here is a list of the capacities of different forms of DVDs:

Format	Capacity	Approx. Movie Time
Single-sided/single-layer	4.38 GB	2 hours
Single-sided/double-layer	7.95 GB	4 hours
Double-sided/single-layer	8.75 GB	4.5 hours
Double-sided/double-layer	15.9 GB	Over 8 hours

You may be wondering why the capacity of a DVD doesn't double when you add a whole second layer to the disc. This is because when a disc is made with two layers, the pits have to be a little longer, on both layers, than when a single layer is used. This helps to avoid interference between the layers, which would cause errors when the disc is played.

4.4 DVD Video

Even though its storage capacity is huge, the uncompressed video data of a full-length movie would never fit on a DVD. In order to fit a movie on a DVD, you need **video compression**. A group called the Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) establishes the standards for compressing moving pictures.

When movies are put onto DVDs, they are encoded in MPEG-2 format and then stored on the disc. This compression format is a widely accepted international standard. Your DVD player contains an MPEG-2 decoder, which can uncompress this data as quickly as you can watch it.

DVD Fact

If an average DVD movie were uncompressed, it would take at least a year to download it over a normal phone line.

4.4.1 The MPEG-2 Format and Data Size Reduction

A movie is usually filmed at a rate of 24 frames per second. This means that every second, there are 24 complete images displayed on the movie screen. American and Japanese television use a format called NTSC, which displays a total of 30 frames per second; but it does this in a sequence of 60 fields, each of which contains alternating lines of the picture. Other countries use PAL format, which displays at 50 fields per second, but at a higher resolution (see How Video Formatting Works for details on these formats). Because of the differences in frame rate and resolution, an MPEG movie needs to be formatted for either the NTSC or the PAL system.

The MPEG encoder that creates the compressed movie file analyzes each frame and decides how to encode it. The compression uses some of the same technology as still image compression does to eliminate redundant or irrelevant data. It also uses information from other frames to reduce the overall size of the file. Each frame can be encoded in one of three ways:

- As an **intra frame** - An intra frame contains the complete image data for that frame. This method of encoding provides the least compression.
- As a **predicted** frame - A predicted frame contains just enough information to tell the DVD player how to display the frame based on the most recently

displayed intra frame or predicted frame. This means that the frame contains only the data that relates to how the picture has changed from the previous frame.

- As a **bidirectional** frame - In order to display this type of frame, the player must have the information from the surrounding intra frame or predicted frames. Using data from the closest surrounding frames, it uses interpolation (something like averaging) to calculate the position and color of each pixel.

Depending on the type of scene being converted, the encoder will decide which types of frames to use. If a newscast were being converted, a lot more predicted frames could be used, because most of the scene is unaltered from one frame to the next. On the other hand, if a very fast action scene were being converted, in which things changed very quickly from one frame to the next, more intra frames would have to be encoded. The newscast would compress to a much smaller size than the action sequence.

If all of this sounds complicated, then you are starting to get a feeling for how much work your DVD player does to decode an MPEG-2 movie. A lot of processing power is required; even some computers with DVD players can't keep up with the processing required to play a DVD movie.

Did you know?

DVDs often have special features hidden on the disc. These "Easter eggs" can be previews of other movies, computer software or music. DVD Review has a listing of some great Easter eggs that viewers have found on DVDs.

4.5 DVD Audio

DVD audio and DVD video are different formats. DVD audio discs and players are relatively rare right now, but they will become more common, and the difference in sound quality should be noticeable. In order to take advantage of higher-quality DVD audio discs, you will need a DVD player with a 192kHz/24-bit digital-to-analog converter (DAC). Most DVD players have only a 96 kHz/24-bit digital-to-analog converter. So if you want to be able to listen to DVD audio discs, be sure to look for a DVD audio player with a 192kHz/24-bit digital-to-analog converter.

DVD audio recordings can provide far better sound quality than CDs. The chart below lists the sampling rate and accuracy for CD recordings and the maximum sampling rate and accuracy for DVD recordings. CDs can hold 74 minutes of music. DVD audio discs can hold 74 minutes of music at their highest quality level, 192 kHz/24-bit audio. By lowering either the sampling rate or the accuracy, DVDs can be made to hold more music. A DVD audio disc can store up to two hours of 6-channel, better than CD quality, 96kHz/24-bit music. Lower the specifications further and a DVD audio disc can hold almost seven hours of CD-quality audio.

Specification	CD Audio	DVD Audio
Sampling Rate	44.1 kHz	192 kHz
Samples Per Second	44,100	192,000
Sampling Accuracy	16-bit	24-bit
Number of Possible Output Levels	65,536	16,777,216

In an audio CD or DVD, each bit represents a digital command telling the DAC what voltage level to output. While an ideal recording would follow the raw waveform exactly, digital recordings sample the sound at different frequencies, and therefore lose some of the data.

Comparison of a raw audio signal to the CD audio and DVD audio output

The graph above shows how the highest quality DVD audio compares to CD audio. You can see that DVD follows the signal more closely, but it's still a long way from perfect.

To get the full experience of the Dolby Digital sound used on many DVDs, you need a home theater system with five speakers, a subwoofer, and a receiver that is either "Dolby Digital ready" or has a built-in Dolby Digital decoder.

If your receiver is Dolby Digital ready, then it does *not* have a Dolby Digital decoder, so you need to buy a DVD player with its own Dolby Digital decoder and 5.1 channel outputs. If you also want your system to be compatible with DTS sound, then your DVD player will need a DTS decoder, too.

Did you know?

Some DVDs carry commentary tracks, in which the filmmaker talks about the movie while it is running. This can be very exciting for true film buffs. DVDs can also contain extra, previously unreleased scenes. And a DVD is sometimes a director's cut -- the film as the director originally intended it.

If your receiver has its own Dolby Digital decoder and DTS decoder, then you don't need a DVD player with 5.1 channel outputs, and you can save some money on cables by using the digital outputs.

5. Blue Laser

5.0 Introduction

The term blue laser is frequently applied to semiconductor laser diode based on gallium nitride. These new devices have applications in many areas ranging from optoelectronic data storage at high-density to medical applications.

5.1 History

Thanks to prior development of many groups, including, most notably, Professor Isamu Akasaki's group, Shuji Nakamura at Nichia Corporation in Anan (Tokushima-ken, Japan) made a series of inventions and developed commercially viable blue and violet semiconductor lasers. The active layer of the Nichia devices was formed from InGaN quantum wells or quantum dots spontaneously formed via self-assembly. Until the mid 1990s, when blue semiconductor lasers were developed, blue lasers were large and expensive gas laser instruments which relied on population inversion in rare gas mixtures and needed high currents and strong cooling. The new invention enabled the development of small, convenient and low priced blue, violet and ultraviolet UV lasers which had not been available before and opened the way for applications such as high-density HD DVD data storage and Blu-ray discs. The shorter wavelength allows it to read discs containing much more information. Blue lasers usually operate at 405 nanometers but in general the operation of these devices was demonstrated between 360 and 480 nm. It is worth noticing that the most popular 405 nm laser is not in fact blue, but appears to the eye as violet, a color for which a human eye has a very limited sensitivity. For display applications, where the "true blue" color is required, the wavelength should be much longer: 450-460 nm. Such lasers are already on the market. The last big challenge is related to the construction of a "true green" InGaN laser (around 530 nm). Many companies demonstrated devices working at only slightly shorter wavelengths: 480- 500 nm - Nichia, Osram OS, Rohm.

5.2 Applications

Areas of application of the blue laser include:

- Telecommunications
- Information technology
- Environmental monitoring
- Electronic equipment
- Medical diagnostics
- Micro projectors, displays and laser

6. How does Blu ray Disc Works?

6.0 Introduction

In 1997, a new technology emerged that brought digital sound and video into homes all over the world. It was called DVD, and it revolutionized the movie industry.

The industry is set for yet another revolution with the introduction of **Blu-ray Discs (BD)** in 2006. With their high storage capacity, Blu-ray discs can hold and play back large quantities of **high-definition video and audio**, as well as photos, data and other digital content.

A current, single-sided, standard DVD can hold **4.7 GB** of information. That's about the size of an average two-hour, standard-definition movie with a few extra features. But a **high-definition movie**, which has a much clearer image), takes up about **five times more bandwidth** and therefore requires a disc with about five times more storage. As TV sets and movie studios make the move to high definition, consumers are going to need playback systems with a lot **more storage capacity**.

Blu-ray vs. DVD Capacity

Blu-ray is the next-generation digital video disc. It can record, store and play back high-definition video and digital audio, as well as computer data. The advantage to Blu-ray is the sheer amount of information it can hold:

A single-layer Blu-ray disc, which is roughly the same size as a DVD, can hold up to 27 GB of data -- that's more than two hours of high-definition video or about 13 hours of standard video.

A double-layer Blu-ray disc can store up to 50 GB, enough to hold about 4.5 hours of high-definition video or more than 20 hours of standard video. And there are even plans in the works to develop a disc with twice that amount of storage.

6.1 Building a Blu-ray Disc

Blu-ray discs not only have more storage capacity than traditional DVDs, but they also offer a new level of interactivity. Users will be able to connect to the Internet and instantly download subtitles and other interactive movie features. With Blu-ray, you can:

- record high-definition television without any quality loss
- instantly skip to any spot on the disc
- record one program while watching another on the disc
- create playlists
- edit or reorder programs recorded on the disc
- automatically search for an empty space on the disc to avoid recording over a program
- access the Web to download subtitles and other extra features

Discs store digitally encoded video and audio information in pits -- spiral grooves that run from the center of the disc to its edges. A laser reads the other side of these pits -- the bumps -- to play the movie or program that is stored on the DVD. The more data that is contained on a disc, the smaller and more closely packed the pits must be. The smaller the pits (and therefore the bumps), the more precise the reading laser must be.

Unlike current DVDs, which use a red laser to read and write data, Blu-ray uses a blue laser (which is where the format gets its name). A blue laser has a shorter wavelength (405 nanometers) than a red laser (650 nanometers). The smaller beam focuses more precisely, enabling it to read information recorded in pits that are only 0.15 microns (μm) ($1 \text{ micron} = 10^{-6} \text{ meters}$) long -- this is more than twice as small as the pits on a DVD. Plus, Blu-ray has reduced the track pitch from 0.74 microns to 0.32 microns. The smaller pits, smaller beam and shorter track pitch together enable a single-layer Blu-ray disc to hold more than 25 GB of information -- about five times the amount of information that can be stored on a DVD.

DVD Vs. Blu-Ray Construction

Each Blu-ray disc is about the same thickness (**1.2 millimeters**) as a DVD. But the two types of discs store data differently. In a DVD, the data is sandwiched between two polycarbonate layers, each 0.6-mm thick. Having a polycarbonate layer on top of the data can cause a problem called **birefringence**, in which the substrate layer refracts the laser light into two separate beams. If the beam is split too widely, the disc cannot be read. Also, if the DVD surface is not exactly flat, and is therefore not exactly perpendicular to the beam, it can lead to a problem known as **disc tilt**, in which the laser beam is distorted. All of these issues lead to a very involved manufacturing process.

6.2 How Blu-ray reads Data?

The Blu-ray disc overcomes DVD-reading issues by placing the data on top of a 1.1-mm-thick polycarbonate layer. Having the data on top prevents birefringence and therefore prevents readability problems. And, with the recording layer sitting closer to the objective lens of the reading mechanism, the problem of disc tilt is virtually eliminated. Because the data is closer to the surface, a hard coating is placed on the outside of the disc to protect it from scratches and fingerprints.

CD vs. DVD vs. Blu-ray Writing

The design of the Blu-ray discs saves on manufacturing costs. Traditional DVDs are built by injection molding the two 0.6-mm discs between which the recording layer is sandwiched. The process must be done very carefully to prevent birefringence.

- The two discs are molded.
- The recording layer is added to one of the discs.
- The two discs are glued together.

Blu-ray discs only do the injection-molding process on a single 1.1-mm disc, which reduces cost. That savings balances out the cost of adding the protective layer, so the end price is no more than the price of a regular DVD.

A BD-ROM disc researcher holds a disc up to the light.

Blu-ray also has a higher data transfer rate -- 36 Mbps (megabits per second) -- than today's DVDs, which transfer at 10 Mbps. A Blu-ray disc can record 25 GB of material in just over an hour and a half.

6.2.1 Formats

Unlike DVDs and CDs, which started with read-only formats and only later added recordable and re-writable formats, Blu-ray is initially designed in several different formats:

- BD-ROM (read-only) - for pre-recorded content
- BD-R (recordable) - for PC data storage
- BD-RW (rewritable) - for PC data storage
- BD-RE (rewritable) - for HDTV recording

6.3 Blu-ray Competitors

Will Blu-ray replace previous DVDs? Its manufacturers hope so. In the meantime, JVC has developed a Blu-ray/DVD combo disc with an approximate 33.5-GB capacity, allowing for the release of video in both formats on a single disc. But Blu-ray is not alone in the marketplace. A few other formats are competing for a share of the DVD market.

The other big player is HD-DVD, also called AOD (Advanced Optical Disc), which was developed by electronics giants Toshiba and NEC. HD-DVD was actually in the works before regular DVD, but it didn't begin real development until 2003.

The advantage to HD-DVD is that it uses the same basic format as the traditional DVD and can therefore be manufactured with the same equipment, saving on costs. HD-DVD matches the storage capacity of Blu-ray. A rewritable, single-layer HD-DVD can hold 15 GB of data, a double-layer disc can hold 30 GB, and a triple-layer disc can hold 45 GB (that's compared to 27 GB and 50 GB for Blu-ray). The read-only versions hold slightly less data. Also, HD-DVD offers the interactive capabilities of Blu-ray, with HDi.

Blu-ray and HD-DVD are the two major competitors in the market, but there are other contenders, as well. Warner Bros. Pictures has developed its own system, called HD-DVD-9. This system uses a higher compression rate to put more information (about two hours of high-definition video) on a standard DVD. Taiwan has created the Forward Versatile Disc (FVD), an upgraded version of today's DVDs that allows for more data storage capacity (5.4 GB on a single-sided disc and 9.8 GB on a double-sided disc). And China has introduced the Enhanced Video Disc (EVD), another high-definition video disc.

There are also professional versions of the blue laser technology. Sony has developed XDCAM and ProData (Professional Disc for Data). The former is designed for use by broadcasters and AV studios. The latter is primarily for commercial data storage (for example, backing up servers).

It seems that the future holds a whole lot more than 25 to 54 GB on a single disc. According to T3: Pioneer goes beyond Blu-Ray, Pioneer is developing an optical

disc that will blow away the hard disc in most of our PCs in terms storage capacity, holding 500 GB of data. How so? Pioneer's lasers are ultraviolet, which have an even shorter wavelength than the blue.

References

http://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/journaldescription.cws_home/933/description

<http://www.howstuffworks.com/>

<http://www.wikipedia.org/>